

SMART ERA

Guidelines for policy audit/D6.1

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Acronyms

Acronym	Description
AEIDL	European Association for Innovation in Local Development
CoR	Committee of the Regions
DG	Directorate General
ENRD	European Network for Rural Development
EPRS	European Parliament Research Service
ESIF	European Structural and Investment Funds
ESPN	European Observation Network for Territorial Development and Cohesion
ISO	International Standards Organisation
ODA	Overseas Development Administration
OECD	Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development
RegHub	Regional Hubs for evaluation of EU public policies
STEEPED	Social, Technological, Economic, Environmental, and Political
EU	European Union

Executive Summary

Deliverable D6.1 "Guidelines for policy audit" will allow pilot responsible partners to analyse the key policy frameworks and the initiatives, strategies, and instruments in their national and regional contexts (with a particular emphasis on EU-supported policies) that are enablers and/or disablers of community-led innovation in rural areas.

The guidelines will also support project partners and other multi-actor participants in identifying key policy concepts and options that are affected by ongoing policy developments.

These Guidelines are aimed at providing a very simple and user-friendly 4-step way for specific territories such as the SMART ERA Pilots, can identify:

- The **issues** that concern them
- The **actors** that are involved in it
- The **barriers** that are in place
- The possible **solutions**

To do so, a **4-step process** is outlined:

1. Identify the **issue** affecting the area (what, who, why, where, when, how)
2. Identify the **actors** (Stakeholder mapping)
3. Identify **positions, opportunities and barriers** (stakeholder positioning)
4. Identify **solutions for policy change** (Scenario building)

For the governance of this process the Pilot Orchestrator is key as it will be the one in charge of driving the policy analysis process described above. Equally the Community Activator has a crucial role in both organising the brainstorming sessions with internal and external actors and stakeholder identification.

This methodology is based on the state of the art of EU guidelines for Better Regulation and the emerging methodologies on rural proofing. This will allow both to carry out policy analysis in different Member States and more fundamentally to reach policy outputs that can be more easily adopted by the EU institutions (and Member States implementing EU legislation) as the basis for policy change.

Lastly, in addition to the guidelines and templates provided specifically to carry out this kind of policy audit, a further set of tools and examples is provided in Annex 1.

1. Context and understanding

1.1. Aim of the Deliverable

SMART ERA will develop **Smart Innovation Packages (SIPs)** that will address the vulnerabilities and exploit the potentials of rural areas where they are applied. These Smart Innovation Packages are designed to be replicable in other rural regions and serve as the basis for a Europe-wide rural innovation strategy. These packages will integrate a long-term impact analysis and sustainability strategy already in place at the end of the project in order to spread out the approach and solutions beyond the project duration and the regions involved.

The starting point are the **six SMART ERA pilots** situated in different countries (Italy, Spain, Finland, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria and the cross-border region between Slovenia, Italy and Croatia) and the socio-economic and environmental challenges they face as rural areas. These rural areas are characterised by different geographic contexts and socio-economic conditions. For the purpose of this project, rural areas are broadly defined following the [Eurostat definition](#) as areas "where more than 50 % of its population lives in rural grid cells". The SIPs will focus on challenges identified comprise key hurdles for the selected rural areas requiring an urgent intervention.

For each pilot, a **Pilot Orchestrator** (in the case of [SMART ERA](#) these [partners](#) are: FBK, UL, UOULU, ANYSOL, SFTH, DPA) and **Community Activator** (PAT, ROTUNDA, C.OULU, +CULTURA, TORS, SEVLIEVO) were selected.

The **Pilot Orchestrator** is a technical partner responsible for deploying its SIP in its own territory, orchestrating pilot activities, and monitoring their execution.

The **Community Activator** is a local Public Authority or Non-Governmental Organization (NGO) that has strong ties with the local residents and stakeholders and a demonstrated experience in engaging them in innovative projects and initiatives. All these couples have long-standing relations and many successful collaborations. In the frame of the piloting, the SIPs will be co-defined, implemented and tested involving local actors.

In SMART ERA, WP6 "Policy analysis and recommendations" aims to support the building of modern community-led innovation policies in rural areas that enhance the "enabling environment" and promote "rural proofing" within the EU multi-level public policies.

In particular, **the key objectives** are:

- i) to develop an **approach and detailed methodology to assess policy and governance frameworks supporting community led innovation** in rural areas.
- ii) to **analyse and map** the evolution and influence of **public policy** frameworks supporting community-led innovation across pilot areas.

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- iii) to co-develop relevant **recommendations**, together with an interactive tool for the modernisation of multi-level policy interventions.

Within this wider context, this document D6.1 “Guidelines for policy audit” has been developed by AEIDL to **enable pilot responsible partners to analyse the key policy frameworks and the initiatives, strategies, and instruments in their national and regional contexts** (with a particular emphasis on EU-supported policies) that are enablers and/or disablers of community-led innovation in rural areas. In addition to project partners, these guidelines will also help other stakeholders outside the project in identifying key policy concepts and options that are affected by ongoing policy developments, as it will be a public and Open Access document.

1.2. Policy Background

In order to introduce **innovative solutions** (practices, technologies, policies, services) in a specific local, and indeed **rural context** it is necessary to understand the **policies** already in place, what are the **actors** (i.e. the stakeholders) that are affected (positive or negative benefit), are interested by it and most importantly those that shape, promote, or block these policies. It should be noted that **Policies** are widely understood as the sum of regulations, decisions, and funding schemes that have been officially agreed to on a particular issue or group of connected issues.

The paradigms behind rural development policies have become increasingly sophisticated over the last couple of decades. As a case in point of this development, Table 1 describes the **Rural Policy 3.0 paradigm from the OECD**, which has subsequently permeated the EU Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas (European Commission, 2022) and indeed the Territorial Cohesion policy thinking of the EU (European Commission, 2024).

This paradigm argues that a key objective of rural policy should be to increase rural competitiveness and productivity in order to enhance the social, economic, and environmental well-being of rural areas. It is more complex and multidimensional than previous approaches to rural policies that were top down or bottom up, mostly reactive and silo-driven. In the present rural approach, policies should focus on enhancing competitive advantages of rural communities. They should also draw on integrated investments and the delivery of basic services (public and privately provided) that are adapted to the needs of diverse types of rural areas.

The Rural Policy 3.0 (and the Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas in the EU context) describes a **partnership-driven approach** that builds capacity at the local level to encourage participation and bottom-up development.

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Table 1 OECD Rural Policy 3.0

	Old Paradigm	New Rural Paradigm (2006)	Rural Policy 3.0 –Implementing the New Rural Paradigm (2016)
Objectives	Equalisation	Competitiveness	Well-being considering multiple dimensions of: i) the economy, ii) society and iii) the environment
Policy focus	Support for a single dominant resource sector	Support for multiple sectors based on their competitiveness	Low-density economies differentiated by type of rural area
Tools	Subsidies for firms	Investments in qualified firms and communities	Integrated rural development approach – spectrum of support to public sector, firms and third sector
Key actors & stakeholders	Farm organisations and national governments	All levels of government and all relevant departments plus local stakeholders	Involvement of: i) public sector – multi-level governance, ii) private sector – for-profit firms and social enterprise, and iii) third sector – non-governmental organisations and civil society
Policy approach	Uniformly applied top-down policy	Bottom-up policy, local strategies	Integrated approach with multiple policy domains
Rural definition	Not urban	Rural as a variety of distinct types of place	Three types of rural: i) within a functional urban area ii) close to a functional urban area, and iii) far from a functional urban area

Source: OECD (2016)

While this approach is more sophisticated than previous rural policy paradigms it conversely makes policy analysis more complex to carry out, as several levels of governance are concerned.

These Guidelines focus primarily on **EU policy analysis**, both because this is meant to support the six SMART ERA pilots across various Member States, but also because the EU is at the source of most regulatory frameworks (EU environmental law, organisation of the food value chain) and financial incentives (i.e. the Common Agricultural Policy and the EU Cohesion Policy) impacting rural areas. Though this deliverable focuses on providing Guidelines for Policy Analysis for the SMART ERA Pilots, it can also be used for **policy analysis of EU Macro-regional strategies**, as the methodology used is a distillation of existing EU guidelines for better regulation and analysis of territorial impacts.

That said, the impact of the EU is more nuanced in some policy areas than others. As it can be seen in Table 2, in most policy areas the EU shares competence with Member States or supports them. Within only a very small set of very high-level policy areas the EU has exclusive competence with all decisions taken in “Brussels”. For most cases, the EU might

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set out the basic rules but the enforcement or the additional rules (*gold-plating*) of financial incentives are defined at national and (quite commonly) at regional level.

Therefore, policy analysis in rural areas is at its core untangling a threat to spell out the different levels of government involved (EU, national, regional, and local) and their respective roles (regulatory, financial, implementation oversight). Identifying these actors and untangling their relationships (or lack of them, i.e. policy silos) it is often at the source of the lock-ins and barriers that prevent sophisticated, cross-sectoral rural policies to function.

Table 2 Areas of EU and shared competence

EU exclusive powers	EU shared powers	EU Supporting powers
The EU has exclusive competence (Art. 3 TFEU)	The EU has shared competences with Member States (Art. 4. TFEU)	The EU can support actions, coordinate, or supplement the actions of Member States (Art. 6 TFEU)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) EU Customs union; (b) EU Competition rules necessary for the functioning of the internal market; (c) Monetary policy for the Member States whose currency is the euro; (d) the conservation of marine biological resources under the Common Fisheries Policy; (e) Common Commercial Policy. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) internal market; (procurement, state aid, technological standards) (b) social policy; (working time, worker's mobility, employment rights) (c) economic, social and territorial cohesion; (EU Structural Funds) (d) agriculture and fisheries, excluding the conservation of marine biological resources; (Common Agricultural Policy, incl. Rural Development) (e) environment; (incl. Environmental impact assessment, protected areas) (f) consumer protection; (g) transport; (incl. organisation of transport services) (h) trans-European networks; (i) energy; (incl. energy efficiency, renewables) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) protection and improvement of human health; (b) industry; (c) culture; (d) tourism; (e) education, vocational training, youth and sport; (f) civil protection; (g) administrative cooperation.

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	<p>(j) area of freedom, security and justice;</p> <p>(k) common safety concerns in certain public health matters</p> <p>Concurrently with Member States programmes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Definition and implementation of Research and Technological development and space programmes, • EU Development cooperation and humanitarian aid. 	
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Furthermore, when analysing complex, multilevel policies the usual approach is to take an objective, analytical and hierarchical approach, whereby the different levels of regulations are analysed in a hierarchical way as in Figure 1.

However, this approach is hardly operational when it comes to carry out policy analysis by local community groups such as SMART ERA where the primary users will be the SMART ERA Pilots, and most particular the Pilot Orchestrators and Community Activators. For that reason, policy analysis from the perspective of local community groups needs to be conducted adopting a subjective approach instead, as in Figure 2.

Actors affected by a policy need not be aware or have training in law and regulation, nor they are necessarily aware of the agencies (domestic or EU) effecting policy levers, nor they will be probably aware of the source of the regulatory or financial framework that is concerning them (or even knowing that such framework does exist somewhere). Furthermore, local actors’ perspective is clouded by their own perceptions and access to information, and therefore **actor-centred policy analysis guidelines** need to be designed from an actor-centred perspective to assist them in identifying what is the problem, what are its dimensions, who has a role or is affected by it and then identify the **barriers, lock ins** and **opportunities** for policy change.

Figure 1 A Schematic hierarchy of EU regulations and directives (Vendt et al., 2022)

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Figure 2 An actor-centric conceptual framework for the study of multilevel governance (Pazos-Vidal, 2019)

The last introductory consideration is that the present guidelines are drawn from the state of the art of EU policy analysis frameworks notably the **EU Better Regulation Guidelines, including Territorial Impact Assessments and Rural Proofing** supplemented operational guidance by the EU Institutions on policy analysis. Though in some Member States there are domestic guidelines (Jones, 2022) for policy analysis or rural proofing, the above-mentioned disproportionate effect of EU regulation and financial frameworks in rural policies as well as the need to have standardised processes that can help compare local impacts in various SMART ERA local Pilots and the ultimate aim to identify barriers and solutions that can by way of policy recommendations D6.3 be made at EU level strongly points towards the need of drawing from the portfolio of EU regulatory analysis tool to draft the present SMART ERA guidelines.

Table 3 EU policy analysis frameworks for rural areas

Better Regulation	Territorial Impact Assessment	Rural Proofing
<p>Official EU process to define new legislation or review existing one (European Commission, 2021).</p> <p>Evidence-based, at expert level (FIT4FUTURE) but also participatory (HaveYourSay consultations).</p> <p>Formal procedures (Regulatory Scrutiny Board, Impact Assessment).</p>	<p>Subset of Better Regulation Framework (methodology developed since 2012, incorporated in 2015) in Tool 34.</p> <p>Considers territorial implications of draft EU legislation or the asymmetric territorial impact of existing legislation.</p>	<p>Stem from Cork 2.0 Declaration (2016).</p> <p>Variant of Territorial Impact Assessment, specifically devoted to rural areas.</p> <p>Incorporated into Better Regulation Guidelines (2021) Tool 34 and Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas (European Commission, 2022).</p>

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	Evidence-based (ESPON TIA methodology, 2020) and participatory (REGHUB).	Various guidelines in place at domestic level, only some tentative guidance at EU level (CoR 2022), ENRD (2022). Focus on participatory evidence gathering.
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Specifically, the aim of these Guidelines is to provide a simplified version of the methodologies for EU policy analysis that are accessible not only for **Pilot Orchestrator** (as the lead actor dealing with policy analysis in a SMART ERA Pilot area) and the **Community Activator** (which will support the Orchestrator by providing the identification of and facilitating exchange with local stakeholders) but also the local actors involved SMART ERA Pilot area, who need not have any prior understanding on policies or policy analysis.

As such the main overarching source of the methodology of the present document are the EU Better Regulation Guidelines themselves (European Commission, 2021, 2023), and the European Parliament own guidelines for policy analysis (Van Woensel, 2021) as well as the European Network for Rural Development (Atteron et al., 2022) and Committee of the Regions (2022) own tentative guidance on rural proofing.

This way not only the most recently available methodological state of the art is captured but also makes it more likely that the results of the policy analysis have been developed using comparable methodologies to those already in place in formal EU policy will make the findings of a SMART ERA Policy audit more likely to be picked up as valid grounds for conducting a formal review of EU policies under the Better Regulation framework.

2. Steps for policy audit

2.1. General considerations: steps and roles

Building upon the existing state of the art of EU policy analysis, these Guidelines provide a simplified set of **4 steps** of **actor-centred policy analysis** that can be directly used by the SMART ERA lock-ins to identify issues (Step 1), identify Actors connected to the issue (Step 2), analysing the actors' respective positions (Step 3), lock ins and barriers, and finally building policy options, alternative scenarios and reporting (Step 4).

The actor centred approach is grounded on building from the SMART ERA Pilot partners collective intelligence, in particular via an iterative set of brainstorming meetings, eventually extended to additional actors that are concerned by the policy issue at hand but are external to the SMART ERA Pilot.

The policy analysis needs to be driven by the Pilot Orchestrator, whereas the Community Activator has a key role in organising the Pilot partner meetings.

2.2. Step 1: Identifying the issue

If a local community group such as a SMART ERA Pilot decides to carry out a policy audit is because there is a perception that there is an **issue** (a problem, a barrier for change or an opportunity) affecting the **area** (the whole territory, its economy, society, environment, culture), and some or all the local **actors**, and that addressing the issue requires a policy change (understood widely as primary legislation or implementing rules, regulatory decisions, or funding, or alternatively the absence of those). This issue might be **context-specific and asymmetric** to that territory or can be comparable with other territories, such as another SMART ERA Pilot.

Therefore, the first step, led by the Pilot Orchestrator is to try to broadly define the issue that will be the subject of the policy analysis in trying to address the basic questions of:

- **What** is the issue?
- **Who** is affected/causing it?
- **Why** is this important?
- **Where** does it happens?
- **When** does it happen? and
- **How** does it happen?

Once this is very broadly defined the Community Activator could organise a **brainstorming session** primarily aimed at member of the SMART ERA Pilot. Brainstorming sessions usually involve a number of actors, to achieve an initial broad understanding of the topic by collectively addressing these questions (what, who, why, where, when and how) in turn to

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gain further depth on the issue that will be subject of the policy analysis. Brainstorming exercises also provides a very initial overview of the wider set of other actors/stakeholders, including those involved or possibly affected. Alternatively, other tools such as [Problem Tree](#) - structural analysis of the causes and effects of an issue or problem – or the Fishbone Diagram method - a visual tool for problem analysis, identifying possible causes, and categorizing cause - could be used for this purpose (WASH et al., 2022).

A further step is to enrich the initial big picture of the policy issue at stake and the ecosystem of actors that are or may be concerned by it, by further characterising all possible factors and dimensions of the issue at stake.

A relatively simple way of doing so is using the so-called STEEPED¹ Wheel (Van Woensel, 2021) that break the issue at hand in seven big factors:

- The **societal** aspects include religion, ethnicity, employment status, financial means, wellbeing, presence of disabilities, and habits. Within the societal aspects related to analysing all implications and possible impacts of a particular type of technology. For instance, the introduction of self-driving cars might be highly appreciated by old age individuals living in rural areas without economically public transport.
- The **technological** aspects include the purpose of a technology and its application, accessibility, efficacy, added value, dual use, research and innovation, and challenges, drawbacks (i.e. undesired consequences, e.g. loss of privacy, less in person social interaction) and technological alternatives (e.g. Rural broadband versus satellite link).
- The **economic** aspects include jobs (creation and losses), value creation, skills dependency, resource dependency, infrastructure dependency and affordability (e.g. cost of introducing hydrogen fuelled cars in rural areas require new services, fuel production plants, and hydrogen equipped filling stations within a reasonable geographical reach, all this need to be economically self-sustainable or requiring external public subsidies).
- The **environmental** aspects include resource efficiency, energy efficiency, water efficiency, recyclability, sustainability, process safety, and product safety.
- The **political and legal** aspects include liability, ethical, demographic and market regulations.
- The **ethical** aspects include respect for people and for the environment, the notions of justice and collective well-being, as well as individual freedom;
- The **demographic** aspects include demographic factors (e.g. age, gender, household status, education level, job type, place/region), as well as demographic trends.

These factors can be ideally broken down further into subfactors (as much as it is necessary or possible to do) as shown in Figure 3. It is important to note however that it is not necessary to fill all subcategories, the full list is provided for illustrative purposes so that the most relevant subcategories can be included.

¹ Social, Technological, Economic, Environmental, and Political

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Figure 3 The STEEPED Wheel Scheme in all of its components (Van Woensel, 2021)

This characterisation can be done in an organic, iterative way with further brainstorming sessions initially with the SMART ERA Pilot members (Step 1) and then involving the wider actors that have been identified (Step 2).

As a result of these discussions, the policy audit lead (in this case the SMART ERA Orchestrator) will be able to put together a table characterising in as much detail as possible the various factors that have been identified, as in Table 4 Template of Policy analysis Factors template below.

Table 4 Template of Policy analysis Factors

Factor	Subfactor (choose from STEEPED diagram Fig 3)	Description	Likely Beneficiary (positive or negative)	Perceived source of authority (regulator, overseer, fund provider)
Political				
Legal				
Environmental				
Economic				
Technological				
Societal				
Ethical				

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Concurrently with the factor identification the Pilot Orchestrator needs to have a better understanding of the territorial impact, essentially addressing the following questions drawn from the **EU Territorial Impact Assessment Better Regulation Tool #34** (European Commission, 2023):

- Does the issue being considered affect economic activity, environment, or people living in cities, rural, cross-border, insular, mountainous, or sparsely populated areas and in the EU outermost regions to a significantly different extent than elsewhere in the EU?
- Is it concentrated in certain areas (e.g. rural), regions, or Member States?
- Does it affect certain areas (e.g. rural, mountain, island, border, peripheral), specific regions or Member States in a disproportionate manner?
- Does it address regions differently according to their own specific characteristics and thus lead to uneven territorial development?
- Does it distort the principle of territorial cohesion (i.e. increase disparities in economic development, social well wellbeing between different EU territories)?

If the answer to any of these questions is positive, the **Territorial Impact Necessity Check** will help assess the need of a more in-depth analysis of the territorial impacts.

To do so there is the possibility to use a **Territorial Impact Assessment Quick Check** is an interactive tool ESPON assessing ex ante the territorial impact of legislations, policies and directives. It allows the user to make a "quick and dirty" ex-ante analysis of the potential impact of EU legislation, policies, and directives on the development of regions, which might be unanticipated and undesirable (ESPON 2020).

The tool combines knowledge gathered by those conducting the policy analysis (ideally a workshop) in a workshop with a set of statistical data describing the characteristics of regions. It is a free tool that can be used interactively, both at step 1 (identification of the problem) as well as step 2 (once all possible actors have been identified in detail) or step 3 (after gathering views from these actors as a result of a workshop or a survey).

Through a series of 5 steps this tool will help the Pilot Orchestrator decides whether a Territorial Impact Assessment is useful for any given policy. Complemented with the detailed evidence gathered in the wider policy analysis process (what is the problems, who are the actors concerned, what are the lock ins and barriers, what are the possible solutions) it can help make a case for a policy change at the end of a policy analysis process, as a One Size Fits all policy does not work for all territories.

2.3. Step 2: Identifying the actors

Once Step 1 an initial set of actors potentially concerned by the issue being subject to policy analysis a more in-depth assessment of those not directly involved in the SMART ERA Pilot is needed.

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2.3.1. Types of actors

Building upon the findings of the brainstorming session and the resulting characterization in Step 1, the Pilot Orchestrator needs to build a more detailed stakeholder mapping covering all actors, which are directly, indirectly or potentially concerned with the policy issue being examined.

To do so, a reliable way is to use the so-called **Six Tests for Stakeholder Identification** contained in Tool #51 of the EU Better Regulation Guidelines (European Commission, 2023, p. 766)

Table 5 Actor identification criteria

Type of Actor	Criteria
Direct Beneficiary	<p><i>Who is directly impacted?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Will their daily/weekly lives will change because of this issue (policy decision/legislation/funding, or absence of it)? • Can they easily avoid being affected by this issue? • Will they have to change their behaviour as a result of this issue?
Indirect beneficiary	<p><i>Who is indirectly impacted?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Will their daily lives change because other actors have been directly affected by this issue? • Will they gain or lose because of changes resulting from this issue happening/not happening?
Potential beneficiary	<p><i>Who is potentially impacted?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In particular circumstances, who will have a different experience as a result of this issue happening/not happening? • Are there individuals or groups who will have to adjust their behaviour if specific conditions apply?
Source of authority	<p><i>Who is the regulator making the decision (or not taking it)?</i> (eg making a rule, awarding a decision/not doing it)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is there any other authority involved in making the decision? How?
Delivery actors	<p><i>Are there vital individuals or groups in the delivery chain?</i> <i>Who is responsible for enforcing it?</i> (if different from regulator)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Whose help is actually needed to make a decision work? • Who will have the ability to obstruct implementation unless co-operating?
Knowledge actors	<p><i>Who thinks they know about the subject?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Who understands the likely impact of this decision on other stakeholders (if different from regulator)? • Who has studied the subject and published views on it? • Who has detailed know-how and expertise that those implementing the decision should also understand? • Are there individuals or groups that will be perceived as knowledgeable on the subject?
Wider Stakeholders	<p><i>Who will show an interest in the subject?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are there organisations, authorities, bodies, or individuals who think they have an interest? • Has anyone been campaigning about the issue? • Is there anyone publishing or broadcasting views on this subject?

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For instance, in a hypothetical example of extension of **rural broadband**, a fairly typical classifications of actors involved this issue could be as follows:

- Direct beneficiaries: local residents benefitting from rural broadband
- Indirect beneficiaries: local businesses, public services
- Potential beneficiaries: new investors making investment decision based on new broadband infrastructure in place
- Source of authority: EU regulator enacting legislation and rules on Broadband Expansion and technical standards, EU legislation and funds on subsidies for broadband expansion, national implementing legislation (parliament) and national competition authority (award decision on broadband expansion) and national government (co-financing EU funding on broadband expansion)
- Delivery Actor: regional government (delivery actor implementing national and EU decisions, or blocking it), other economic actors in favour -or against- broadband exemptions to safeguard their own business interests.
- Knowledge actors: could be the local university rural research centre that provides knowledge to choose the most appropriate form of broadband expansion and identity issues.
- Wider stakeholders: for instance, members of the local community concern about the loss of local character as a result of technological change.

NOTE: Step 1 and Step 2 can be done in a more complex matrix. This is particularly relevant when carrying out rural proofing as there is a complex set of factors having a knock-on effect in territorial development, thus making individual, policy specific and silo approaches to policy analysis unsuitable for impact assessment in a given territory or local case study

2.3.2. Identifying authorities and delivery agents

In policy analysis a particularly important actor that needs to be identified as much and as at an earlier stage are those that we have termed source of authority (i.e. most commonly the public authority or authorities that set out legislation, implementing rules, interpretative, or statutory guidelines or technical standards), often in conjunction with delivery actors in charge of enforcement (e.g. responsible to award decisions or subsidies), which may be a different authority from that setting out the rules. In some cases, delivery actors need not be a public authority but another organisation or entity (voluntary, chartered, social economy, etc.) to which public authority has entrusted the enforcement of a public policy, setting up guidelines or technical standards (e.g. ISO organisations).

As mentioned in the introduction and in the above example on rural broadband it is particularly challenging to disentangle sources of authority as policies, particularly those

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emanating from the EU is very much fragmented and indeed shared between various levels of government (Multilevel Governance).

Example: Identifying Authority and Delivery actors in fiscal benefits for depopulating rural areas

In 2022 the EU has agreed to set out new Regional Aid Guidelines that give special treatment (for instance fiscal incentives) to areas affecting to 10% depopulation loss over the previous decade, this had to be set out by the corresponding Member State in their Regional Aid Map (and agreed by the Commission) whereas designing the specific schemes might fall to a national or regional authority and it is ultimately the local authority that administers the scheme.

From the point of view of the local actor as direct, indirect or potential beneficiary it is not immediately clear who is responsible for what and if there is a lock in that prevent that policy from being applied where it can be in the regulatory and decision-making chain.

From an actor-centred perspective the most practical way is to follow up the decision chain, as the local authority to award a scheme needs to refer to the rules that empower them to do so, and which authority has enacted them, in turn these national plans and specific national administration in charge of them need to specifically refer to the EU legislation and European Commission Directorate General that deemed these rules compliant with the EU Single Market.

So following bottom up the paper trail can be an easy and practical way to identify both authority and delivery actors as well as possible lock ins and barriers that remain in place (Pazos-Vidal, 2022).

Once the mapping of stakeholders has been completed a table such as the below Table 6 Template needs to be put together by the pilot orchestrator.

Table 6 Template for Actor identification

Types of actors	Sub-types	Who?	Why?	Where?	When?	How?
Beneficiaries	Direct Beneficiary					
	Indirect Beneficiary					
	Potential Beneficiary					
Decision Makers	Source(s) of Authority					
	Delivery Actor					
Stakeholders	Knowledge Actors					
	Wider stakeholders					

2.4. Step 3: identifying positions, opportunities and barriers

Once the stakeholders have been identified in Step 2, the next step is to identify their respective positioning as regards to the topic (problem, challenge, opportunity) that is being

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analysed. There are several ways of doing so, from documental analysis (e.g. public statements, legislation, policy documents), stakeholder group meetings, a survey to them or a combination of those (Asdal & Reinertsen, 2022).

Organising a meeting with the wider set of actors identified in Stage 2 is a particularly efficient way to understand the nuances of each actor position. Unlike the meetings with members of the Pilot organised in Stage 1, this meeting should be facilitated by the Pilot Orchestrator as the lead of the Policy Analysis exercise. However, the meeting dynamics could be very similar to the meeting in Stage 1, only with a wider set of actors being represented. Still, in many occasions it might not be logistically feasible to bring all identified actors together, or they would be too remote or unwilling to meet, hence the value of combining stakeholder meeting with documentary analysis and surveys to all identified actors.

2.4.1. Identifying actors’ positions

Out of this a very simple table of stakeholder positioning can be used. One much used for local development worldwide is due to its simplicity that provide by ODA (1995) as it can be summarised in a very synthetic table such as in the example as in Table 7 below.

Table 7 Example of Actor identification: Stakeholder positions in EU Structural Funds 2014-2020

Actor	Position	Detail
Member State	+ -	Increase freedom to design priorities. Avoid binding and detailed Partnership obligations, conditionalities.
EU Commission (Secretariat General)	+ +	Use Structural Funds (ESIF) as a way to influence Europe 2020 agenda implementation. Increase consistency via Common Strategic Framework as a way to increase legitimacy over the EU budget.
DG REGIO	+ + -	Keep substantive budget. Be the lead DG in ESIF and Partnership negotiations. Avoid reduction of budget towards thematic funds.
DG AGRI	+ -	Keep managing Rural Development fund. Resist CSF, ESIF Common provisions.
DG EMPL	+ + -	Increase share of ESIF, at least 20% ring-fence for ESF. Increase visibility, separate identity of ESF. Resist any provision that undermining identity of ESF, e.g. Multi-fund
Thematic DGs	+ + -	Increase budget to the detriment of ESIF. Alternatively increase access of ESIF to finance own policies. Resist CSF, Integrated approach to be directly binding on them.
European Parliament	+ + + -	Increase ESIF budget. Increase ability to scrutinise and accountability over ESIF implementation. Widen legitimacy from LRAs (territorial instruments, partnership provisions). Resist MS watering down regulations, cut down budget.
Committee of the Regions	+ -	Increase budget, partnership provisions, CoR own scrutiny role. Reduction of budget, conditionalities.
Local and Regional Authorities	+ + -	Access EU funds. Territorial Development instruments (CLLD, ITI), sub-delegation. Additional audit/regulatory burden, Conditionalities.

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Civil Society	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Increase earmarked funds. + Increased partnership provisions (visibility of decisions, access to decision-making). - Limit additional obligations (audit, co-financing) in exchange for enhanced partnership provisions or fund allocation.
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Source: Pazos-Vidal (2014).

However, this assessment of the various actors' position is too static and a more dynamic picture of their relationships (hierarchical, partnership) or interdependencies (top down, bottom-up) and attitudes (constructive, resistance) can be created to better illustrate them, as shown in the Figure 4 example.

Figure 4 Example diagram with broad stakeholder relationships

2.4.2. Stakeholder matrix

Depending on the availability of information or feedback from the positions of each actors a more fine-tuned assessment (stakeholder matrix) can be created by exploring the **detail positions relationships and biases** of each actor.

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Table 8 Template for detailed stakeholder matrix

Name	Type of Actor (as in Step 2)	Role and Importance	Interest pursued	Power and resources for influencing	Formal and Informal Linkages with other actors	Incentives	Bias

Source: adaptation from ODA (1995) and European Commission, 2012).

In the above mapping characterising, the respective actor biases may be difficult to be identified and quite subjective for the Orchestrator to do so, as the actor may be reluctant to fully spell out its views. However, to the extent that is possible it is useful information to have. Again, a useful guidance of the types of bias is provided by the European Parliament own guidance (Van Woensel, 2021).

Figure 5 The bias wheel, a tool for becoming aware of biases in policy analysts' tasks

Source: Van Woensel (2020)

2.5. Step 4 Identifying solutions

The last step is carried out based on the information gathered in previous steps and it aims at providing one or several recommendations of **options for policy change** (significant changes or minor adjustment) and the various scenarios that could emerge as a result.

2.5.1. Options for policy change

The broad categories for policy options can be drawn from the **EU Better Regulation Tool #34** on Territorial Impact assessment, already cited, are as follows:

1. *Adjust the policy for the entire Union (or country, or region) or some of its parts;*
2. *Grant more time to implement a policy in some territories or some sectors/actors;*
3. *Exempt from the policy those actors or territories that are unaffected by the problem the policy aims to address;*
4. *Use existing policies to address asymmetric territorial impacts (for example by using Cohesion Policy, etc);*
5. *Create a new instrument to address asymmetric territorial impacts if/when they arise.*

Therefore, a policy option needs to have as end result one or several of these options.

Because, more often than not, the issue being analysed might involve more than one policy and more than one level of governance answering the above set of questions can be refined further using the [Subsidiary Assessment Grid](#) (European Commission, 2018)

2.5.2. Scenario Building

Scenario building should be constructed to understand the levers and barriers for policy change. Scenarios can be drafted by building on the combination of outcomes of the analysis of the available evidence and the outcomes of the brainstorming exercise in Step 1 and wider Stakeholder meeting and engagement in Step 3. These need to be prepared by the Orchestrator but should ideally be supported by policy analysis (such as the Knowledge actors identified in Stage 2). A small team of policy analysts can also prepare them.

Ideally this scenario building should receive input from the wider actors identified in Step 3 and validated by the SMART ERA Pilots. Such scenario building needs to gather all available evidenced and seek to address the following questions for each of the possible policy options:

- In order to achieve policy change X, who is the primary actor responsible for taking that decision?

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- Who stands to benefit or be negatively affected by change X?
- What would be the knock-on effect of change X in the other identified actors?
- What would be the consequence in policy Y of this change in policy X?
- What would be the actors affected positively or negatively by this knock-on effect change in policy Y?

This is why the questionnaire for the above-mentioned stakeholder group/survey or documentary analysis need to respond to the previous questions. In essence, this allows to consider adjusting policy by looking at the principles of subsidiarity and proportionality:

- The **subsidiarity principle** helps determine whether it is justified for the Union to act within the shared or supporting competences it has been given under the Treaties or whether it is more appropriate that Member States act at the appropriate national, regional, or local levels.
- The **proportionality principle** helps ensure that the intensity of the legislative obligations or policy approach match the intended objectives of the policy or legislation. This means that the content and form of Union action (and likewise national and subnational authorities) must not go beyond what is necessary to achieve the intended objective

For illustrative purposes, If you've ever needed to explore the full impact of a proposed change, these dependencies and interrelations can be illustrated by a diagram of the direct and indirect future consequences of a particular change or development. This is where the Futures Wheel can help. This visual tool gives you a structured way of brainstorming the direct and indirect consequences of a decision, event, or trend. In '[The Futures Wheel](#)' the change that has been identified is placed in the middle and is a way of organising thinking and questioning about the future— then small spokes are drawn wheel-like from the centre. Primary impacts or consequences are written at the end of each spoke.

Next, the secondary impacts of each primary impact form a second ring of the wheel and future rings with more knock-on effects can be added until the most complete picture of effects and consequences is identified. Therefore, this is not just a useful way to illustrate in the final Policy Analysis report the consequences of the intended changed, but also this provide as template that can be used in the above-mentioned brainstorming sessions to help collectively identify the possible consequences of a given scenario.

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Figure 6 The Futures Wheel. Source: EPRS (2021) adapted from Glenn (2009).

2.5.3. Final Report

A final report should summarise all these findings and the 4 steps policy analysis taken to reach the possible conclusions of recommending recommend policy change or adjustment. Quite clearly, the value of such policy analysis is not to expect immediate policy change but to persuade the actors that participated in the exercise, or those external actors whose actions and positions were examined, that policy change may be needed. The fact that the methodologies used are a simplified version of the policy tools available at EU level should make the output of such policy analysis particularly enticing for EU institutions to consider applying an official better regulation assessment.

The SMART ERA policy analysis, conducted by the Pilot Orchestrator using this deliverable, will inform the policy recommendations to be developed at the end of the project in D6.3.

Likewise, they can be used throughout the project by way of:

- SMART ERA communication and dissemination activities,
- discussion material for the various policy events that will be carried out by the project or in partnership with other projects.
- Feed into the various policy consultations ([Have your Say](#), [Better Regulation consultations](#), parliamentary, European Committee of the Regions, and European Economic and Social Committee hearings as well as the equivalent processes of legislative simplification and rural proofing that are in place in several Member States)²

² For a reference of these domestic systems it is worth refer to

3. Conclusions

These Guidelines are aimed at providing a very simple and user-friendly 4-step way for local communities such as the SMART ERA Pilots, supported by the Pilot Orchestrator and Community Activator can identify the issues that most affect them and to identify the factors, actors and barriers that are influencing it, for then to suggest possible solutions. As the methodology is based on the existing EU guidelines for better regulation and rural proofing, this makes it much easier to apply across Member States and to provide results that can be understood at EU level, making it more likely that recommendations can be turned in policy changes by decision makers. Annex 1 provides further examples to refine the analysis. To sum up, the below policy audit Checklist provides a summary of all steps to be taken.

Table 9 Policy Audit's Checklist for SMART ERA Pilot Regions

Step	Task	Status
1. Identify the issue affecting the area	Address key basic questions about the given issue (what, who, why, where, when, how)	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Organise a brainstorming session to move from initial broad understanding to further depth on the issue	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Perform a STEEPED Wheel analysis	<input type="checkbox"/>
	[Optional] Address the questions of the EU Territorial Impact Assessment Better Regulation Tool #34	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Identify the actors	Perform detailed Stakeholder mapping using the Six Tests for Stakeholder Identification contained in the Better Regulation Guidelines Tool #51	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Identifying authorities and delivery agents from the Stakeholder mapping table	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Identify positions, opportunities and barriers	Develop a stakeholder positioning table illustrating stakeholders' respective positions, opportunities, barriers, and incentives	<input type="checkbox"/>
	[Optional] Organise a meeting with actors identified in Step 2 to understand nuances of each actor position	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Identify solutions for policy change	Build scenarios (based on evidence from stakeholder meetings in Steps 1 and 3, and policy analysis performed by knowledge actors identified in Step 2)	<input type="checkbox"/>
	[Optional] Use 'The Futures Wheel' to visualize impacts, dependencies, and interrelations of alternative scenarios	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Illustrate the steps undertaken and summarise findings/conclusions in a final report	<input type="checkbox"/>

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